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“A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON HAPPINESS OF GOVERNMENT/AIDED AND SELF FINANCE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS OF U. P. BOARD”

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A Comparative Study of the Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Happiness of Government/Aided and Self Finance Secondary School Teachers of U. P. Board

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to compare the effect of emotional intelligence on happiness of Govt/Aided and Self finance secondary school teachers. Survey Method was conducted on a random sample of 200 secondary school teachers of Bareilly District. Emotional Intelligence Scale made by Anukool Hyde & Sanjyot Path consisting of 34 items and Happiness Scale made by Pranjal Buragohen consisting of 40 items in the scale were used for data collection. Data were analyzed through two-way ANOVA test. Findings showed that there was no significant influence of level of emotional intelligence on happiness & type of institutions of secondary school teachers. But significant influence of interaction of type of institutions and emotional intelligence on happiness of secondary school teachers was found.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Happiness, Type of Institute, Secondary School Teachers.

Introduction:

Emotional Intelligence is claimed to be important factor which determines success and well being in life. Emotional Intelligence is very much related to mental health of the person. According to most of the psychologist, there are basically six types of emotions; Anger, fear, disgust, surprise, happiness and sadness. Research in recent years has validated that emotional intelligence is significant in predicting a number of real- life outcomes, such as occupational & academic success and quality of interpersonal relations (Lam & Kirloy *et al.*).

Emotional Intelligence (EI) was first studied by Thorndike within the framework of the concept of social intelligence. Thorndike defined social intelligence as “understanding and managing others.”(Rastegar,M. 2009). EI is also a part of Gardner’s view of social intelligence, which he refers to as personal intelligence. Like social intelligence, personal intelligences (divided into

inter- and intra- personal intelligence) include knowledge about others. The concept was popularized in a best- selling book entitled Emotional Intelligence (Goleman, 1995). Emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive, appraise and express emotions accurately and adaptively. (Khosla, Dokania, 2010). People with high EI are proven to be more successful in the workplace because they can understand their emotions and why they behave properly. They can use their emotions as clues to what their body and mind are trying to tell them (Tschiesche. K, 2012).

Happiness is based on a person’s attitude and refers to a pleasant condition that this condition comes from the positive experience, emotions and happiness in life. Naturally, such a fun and pleasant condition associated with no depression, irrational beliefs, anxiety, anger and other negative emotions. Evidence suggests that happiness produces energy, vitality and dynamic life. Happiness as a shield can protect human against mental stress and guarantee their physical and mental health (Hills & Argyleand, 2001). Lybomirske et al. (2005), believed that happiness, reduce stress and increases person’s ability to do their work. Kawamoto(1999), believed that increasing the happiness associated with improve of health status, sleep, memory, family relationships, friendships, mental health status and ultimately an increase in appetite.

Emotional Intelligence:

Figure-1: Factor of emotional intelligence

Happiness:

Figure-2: Dimensions of happiness

Significance of the study:

In the present time and recent years the term emotional intelligence increasingly has been expanding especially in its application in Education. Emotional intelligence is a concept increasingly recognized in the social psychology literature and psychological wellbeing. A person who has emotional intelligence gives order and stability to his life in such a way that with high emotional intelligence, the person will experience less negative events in his/her life, based on the results of Richardson and Collaborators research as quoted by ismaili. Mayer and Salovy research shows that emotional intelligence is related to mental health components. In the shining of all above studies the present study is a tryout to investigate the effect of emotional intelligence on happiness of secondary school teachers. The results will be helpful to adjust the teachers with pleasure. The happiness is well condition for more productivity in teaching and all other professions. So the study will set up a positive view toward the inter relation of emotional intelligence and happiness.

Statement of the problem:

A Comparative Study of the Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Happiness of Government/Aided and Self Finance Secondary School Teachers of U. P. Board

Objective of the study:

1. To study the effect of emotional intelligence on happiness of secondary school teachers.
2. To find out the effect of type of institutions on happiness of secondary school teachers.
3. To find out the effect of interaction between emotional intelligence & type of institutions on happiness of secondary school teachers.

Hypothesis:

H1- There is no significant influence of emotional intelligence on happiness of secondary school teachers.

H2- There is no significant influence of type of institutions on happiness of secondary school teachers.

H3- There is no significant influence of interaction of emotional intelligence & type of institutions on happiness of secondary school teachers.

Delimitation of the study:

The study was delimited to 200 secondary school teachers of teachers working in UP board (Self finance school & Govt.+Aided School) secondary schools located in Bareilly district of Uttar Pradesh state only.

Methodology:

The investigator randomly selected 200 teachers from 12 secondary schools located in Bareilly of Uttar Pradesh state. The sample comprised of 94 self finance UP Board school teachers and (39 female +55 male) and 106 Govt.+Aided UP Board school teachers (51 female+ 55 male). Survey method was used for data collection. Emotional Intelligence Scale by Anukool Hyde & Sanjyot Pethe and Happiness Questionnaire by Pranjal Buragohain, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Education Dibrugarh University are used to collect data from sample teachers of secondary school of Bareilly. Emotional Intelligence Scale consists of 34 items in 10 dimensions and Happiness Questionnaire consists of 40 items in 5 dimensions. The data were analyzed using statistical techniques such as mean, standard deviation and F- test.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:**Table-1.1 Descriptive Statistics**

	Group EI	Institute	Mean	Std. Dev.	N
Happiness	Low	Govt.	152.00	15.82	21
		SF	158.43	15.49	35
		Total	156.02	15.79	56
	Moderate	Govt.	156.59	16.34	51
		SF	147.95	20.42	42
		Total	152.69	18.70	93
	High	Govt.	157.56	10.54	34
		SF	145.12	23.00	17
		Total	153.41	16.67	51
	Total	Govt.	155.99	14.62	106
		SF	151.34	19.84	94
		Total	153.81	17.38	200

Table- 1.2 Summary of ANOVA of Happiness

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F
Group EI	428.007	2	214.004	.745
Institute	1032.401	1	1032.401	3.594
Group EI*Institute	2639.419	2	319.709	4.594*
Error	55732.976	194	287.283	
Total	60145.395	199		

*Significant at 0.05 level

H1- There is no significant influence of emotional intelligence on happiness of secondary school teachers.

From above table-1.2, it is revealed that F- value (.745) is found to be non significant at 0.05 level of significance. Thus the null Hypothesis (H1) ‘There is no significant influence of level of emotional intelligence on happiness of secondary school teachers’ is accepted.

H2- There is no significant influence of type of institutions on happiness of secondary school teachers.

On the contrary to it, F- value (3.594) for main effect of type of institutions on happiness is found to be non significant at .05 significance level. It denotes that type of institutions does not affect their happiness significantly. So, null hypothesis (2) that ‘There is no significant influence of type of institutions on happiness of secondary school teachers’ is accepted.

The

H3- There is no significant influence of interaction of emotional intelligence & type of institutions on happiness of secondary school teachers.

Table-1.3 **Pairwise Comparisons**

Dependent Variable: Happiness

Group EI	Institute	Institute	Mean Difference
Low	Govt.	SF	-6.43
Moderate	Govt.	SF	8.64*
High	Govt.	Sf	12.44*

*The mean difference is significant at the .05 level

From above table-1.3, it is revealed that F- value (4.594) is found to be significant at 0.05 level. In the light of above mentioned results, the null hypothesis, “there is no significant influence of interaction of emotional intelligence & type of institutions on happiness of secondary school teachers” is rejected.

Although the main effect of emotional intelligence on Govt./aided and self-finance secondary school teachers was found to be non-significant, but their interaction is significant. This implies that some groups (Low, Moderate and High) of emotional intelligence mayinterF- value for the

interaction between level of emotional intelligence and type of institutions is significant, it indicate that the difference between the mean of Govt. & Self Finance teachers in the high, moderate and low emotional intelligence differ significantly from one another. Significant interaction effect between emotional intelligence and type of institutions.

According to table the mean of low emotional intelligence self finance teachers and low emotional intelligence government teachers, is 158.43 and 152 respectively. It indicate that low emotional intelligence self finance teachers are happier than low emotional intelligence government teachers. Low emotional intelligence government teachers are facing adjustment problem so they are not happy.

The mean of Moderate emotional intelligence government teachers and moderate emotional intelligence self finance teachers, is 156.59 and 147.95 respectively. It indicate that moderate emotional intelligence teachers are more happy than moderate emotional intelligence self finance teacher. M.E.I. government teachers are adjusting themselves in school invironment.

The mean of high emotional intelligence government teachers and high emotional intelligence self finance teachers, is 157.56 and 145.12 respectively. It indicate that government teachers are more happy than self finance teachers because government teachers work in stress free environment and are permanently settle while self finance teachers face the pressure of management and are temporary placed.

Estimated Marginal Means of HAPPINES

Estimated Marginal Means of HAPPINES

Conclusion

According to analysis of data through interaction and mean we may conclude the results that government teachers are happier than self-finance teachers because government job is permanent and they work without any pressure and fear. While job of a self finance teachers is a temporary based and low salary paying. Self-finance teachers faced the burden and pressure of management also so they are not happy at all.

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